

Data and documentaries: Methodological hybridisations in activism

Abstract: Hybridisation permeates all fields of communication; documentaries are not an exception. One example is *The Left-to-die Boat*, by Forensic Architecture, an audio-visual account of how 63 refugees lost their lives in 2011 when their ship was adrift in the waters of Libya. *The Left-to-die Boat* combines documentary techniques with data analysis and visualisations to expose a tragedy, change migration policies and sustain court cases. Based on critical data and documentary studies, this article inspects the methodological hybridisation proposed by FA in seven documentaries. The questions are how does FA hybridise? What are the outcomes of this hybridisation? The analysis links these documentaries' characteristics with functions and outcomes, offering a taxonomy that can be employed beyond this study. The findings indicate that activism is taking multidimensional forms, blurring the boundaries separating documentaries, data science and art in search of impact.

Keywords: hybridisation, methodologies, documental, human rights, activism, big data

Hybridisation in activism, journalism and documentaries

Hybridisation –understood broadly as a mixture— is not a new phenomenon in documentaries. An example is the docu-soap (portmanteau of *documentary* and *soap opera*) in the 90s in the United States (McNair, 2009), which not only integrated the language of television dramatization in journalism, but also it blurred the lines that divided fiction and nonfiction, producing a ‘bastard union’ (Lünenborg, 2002, p. 2). Docu-soaps mainly include real-life sagas of ordinary people (Izod, Kilborn, & Hibberd, 2000). In addition to talking about family issues, in 1973, *An American Family*, a series broadcasted by the US Public Broadcasting Service (PBS) after editing 300 hours of raw images, showed for the first time on television the tribulations of an openly homosexual person (PBS, 2002). Other forms of hybridisation in audio-visual non-fiction include Dan Archer’s exploration of journalism, comics and immersive techniques, such as augmented reality (Archer, 2017). These explorations are especially interesting for activism since virtual reality formats provoke greater empathy than photography and text, and a better possibility for participants to engage in a ‘political or social action’ (Sacristán, 2017). The growing access and popularity of digital techniques and tools have made audio-visual hybridisation even more multifaceted in how it constructs reality and establishes a dialectic between objectivity, subjectivity and ‘the appearance of truth’ (Bort Gual, 2010, p. 11). This article is focused on Forensic Architecture (FA for short), a multidisciplinary research centre based in Goldsmiths, University of London, and its oceanographic team –called Forensic Oceanography (FO)—, and seven of their hybridising projects, including *The Left-to-die Boat*.

The Left-to-die Boat (Figure 1) is an eighteen-minute audio-visual story that tells how 63 refugees lost their lives in 2011 when their ship was adrift in the coastal waters of Libya. Defying classification, *The Left-to-die Boat* combines documentary techniques

(eg voice-over, soundtrack, recreations and direct interviews) with data analysis, visualisations and a map that takes up most of the screen. Shedding light on an ignored tragedy, the story was the basis for a campaign demanding change in European migration policies and offered evidence on human rights violations put forward in several court cases (Pezzani and Heller 2011).

[Figure 1 about here]

Figure 1: Film still, *Liquid Traces – The Left-to-die Boat Case*, Forensic Oceanography, 17 minutes, 2012. Courtesy of Forensic Oceanography.

The digital can both enhance politics (i.e. facilitating existing practices) and enable new forms of politics (i.e. generating novel forms of political engagement) (Kurban, Peña-Lopez, & Haberer, 2016). Data activism is a manifestation of digital-based, bottom-up politics that can take both paths. One example of the former type of activism is the *España en llamas* campaign by Civio (Garcia Rey & Garrido, 2016); the map showing information on fires in Spain –a data visualisation— supports an existing campaign to fight against deforestation, land grabbing and illegal conflagrations. FA’s documentaries can be considered an activist data organisation that uses the data infrastructure as an enabling means for counter-forensic investigations, a new activist endeavour. While standard forensic practices are concerned with gathering evidence to elucidate police cases, FA uses the same methods and tools to uncover how the police, armies and authorities have abused people’s rights. Namely, FA is innovating using the data infrastructure, together with other technologies, to generate counter-forensic investigations.

FA can be considered too a geotivist organisation since it puts maps and data in the centre of its strategies to analyse human rights abuses and communicate its investigations’ findings (Gutierrez, 2018). Activism is understood here as an activity, individual or collective, intended to inspire, guide or steer political, social, economic or environmental change to improve or amend an injustice. Meanwhile, the data infrastructure includes the processes, relationships, hardware and software needed to turn data into useful and actionable information (Gutierrez 2018a).

Hybridisation is a feature of contemporary activism, as it today adopts complex and crossbreed forms, which mix old and new, physical and digital, human and nonhuman (i.e. robots), as well as corporate and alternative technologies to analyse data, coordinate action, mobilise, visualise data and communicate messages and findings (Trere, 2019). FA’s proposals fit into this universe of contemporary activism. Indeed, FA uses ballistics and documentary, architectural, journalistic, spatial, forensic, artistic and surveillance techniques that belong to different disciplines and practices, including art, architecture, cartography, film, oceanography, engineering, surveillance and detection, and criminology, to explore and report cases of brutality and violations of human rights on behalf of victims, human rights organisations, prosecutors and journalistic media organisations (Forensic Architecture, 2018a).

For example, to determine the morphology of the clouds generated by the bombs dropped on Rafah in 2014, FA studied the devices designed by the fourteenth century architect Filippo Brunelleschi to project the sky on the interior surface of a dome and the grids proposed in the nineteenth century by John Ruskin, historian of art and architecture (Weizman, 2017, pp. 191–192). Figure 2 shows the reconstruction of the cloud formations caused by the bombs dropped in Rafah.

[Figure 2 around here]

Figure 2: Film still, *The Bombing of Rafah*, Forensic Architecture, 4:30 minutes, 2015. Courtesy of Forensic Architecture.

To investigate the bomb attack of 2014 against the city of Rafah, in the Occupied Palestinian Territories, FA collaborated with Amnesty International (AI), which, in turn, has experience in addressing the dissemination of issues related to human rights through film (Garcia Giribet, 2019). In this attack, at least 65 people were killed, most of them minors (Burke, Borger, & Lewis, 2014). The assault is tackled in the FA 4:30 minute video by resorting to real images of the bombs falling on the city from news media footage and images in social media platforms, reconstructions of the formation of the gases created by the impacts, a three-dimension (3D) model of the city, testimonies of the victims in the first person and the voice of a narrator who recites the facts. The three-dimensional model allows FA to identify where the missiles fell and determine the intensity of the attack, and to put the narrated facts and real-life images in context for audiences. This investigation is one of the documentaries that are employed here to illustrate how the mixture of techniques, languages and narratives occurs in activism, also showing how FA is pushing the forefront of hybridisation in activism and the documentary.

Although there is no consensus about what a *documentary* is, each of the FA videos can be described as one. Documentaries, in general, refer here to non-fiction audio-visual narratives that have educational, awareness or mobilisation objectives. However, the documentary is a ‘diffuse concept’, which includes narratives that adopt diverse, highly heterogeneous forms (Nichols, 2001, p. 21). They can adopt different techniques, themes and styles while being recognised as documentaries; it is a space in constant transformation (Nichols, 2001, p. 21). Hybridisation is also one of the documentary’s peculiarities too. Zimmermann conceives the documentary as a changing ecosystem of mixed practices, comprising diverse techniques, groups, politics and social struggles (Zimmermann, 2019). While there is no consensus on what a documentary is, there is an accord that documentaries claim an association to reality and facts. Nichols notes that ‘the appearance of an image is shaped or determined by what it records’ (Nichols, 2001, p. 35), while Winston recognises the documentary’s aspiration to apprehend truths (Winston, 1995, p. 11). This matter is essential for FA’s deployment of images and sounds as reality-based evidence, even as their kaleidoscopic proposals reveal that these images and sounds are relative, mediated and continuously challenged.

As said, FA sits at the shifting intersection of activism and documentaries. FA's uniqueness is that its methodologies and the tools employed to implement them are the protagonists in all its documentaries; each video is both the story of a case of abuse, a killing or violation of human rights, and a detailed demonstration of how the data on which the report is based were collected and analysed to generate credibility. This article deals with FA's methodological hybridisation to explore the mixture in approaches and tools that FA uses to analyse data and tell audio-visual stories.

This study is focussed on the methodological and tool hybridisation displayed by FA. It is based on a previous exploration of FA documentaries from a cinematographic and reception perspective (Gutierrez, forthcoming 2020), in which these documentaries are examined as testimony and truths-generating artefacts at a moment when activists are being hounded everywhere (e.g. Gunia 2019); big media organisations are retreating their foreign correspondents (Garton Ash 2010); citizen journalists have to do the job of professional journalists (BBC 2012), and fake news congest the social media platforms. From this perspective, FA employs two strategies to shape its narratives and their impact beyond the film: the generation of meta-narratives –which tell the counter-stories of how FA investigators know what happened—, and transculturality –which emerges as multilingualism, the creation of intermediary characters and places, and the development of new communicative spaces inside and outside the stories (Gutierrez, forthcoming 2020).

Meanwhile, this paper utilises content and comparative analysis of seven of FA's short films identify how FA hybridises approaches and tools. The seven documentaries studied here include *Killing in Umm al-Hiran*, *Chemical Attacks in Al Lataminah*, *Torture and Detention in Burundi*, *The Seizure of the Juventa*, *Torture in Saydnaya Prison*, *The Bombing of Rafah* and *The Left-to-die Boat*. Table 1 details the facts investigated, their duration, where they can be found, and the techniques employed by each documentary. The selection of the seven documentaries, out of more than forty FA has produced so far, is based on criteria of variety in duration, themes, actors and methods, as well as their representativeness.

[Table 1 around here]

Table 1: Documentaries, investigated incidents, duration, URL and methods.
Elaboration by the author based on Forensic Architecture (2018)

These are all short films since they last between a few to about thirty minutes. Although there is no consensus either about how to define them, short films enjoy enormous popularity given the possibilities offered by digital technologies both to produce and to broadcast this type of projects through platforms such as YouTube, Yahoo! Video and Joost. FA makes extensive use of these technologies, and then offers these videos freely on its website and in public exhibitions, as seen next.

The article is organised as follows: first, there is an analysis of the methodological and tools hybridisations in FA and FO, focussing on their main hybridisation strategies

including a) a combination of image complex and synchronisation, b) fluid dynamics mixed with other techniques, and c) the blend of 3D modelling, animation and sound analysis. Second, a classification of these strategies is offered as a heuristic tool which can be employed in other analyses beyond this one. And third, the conclusion and discussion is a reflection on what these innovations could mean for activism today.

Methodological hybridisation in FA

Their methodological hybridisation makes Forensic Architecture's videos challenging to classify. For example, FA documentaries do not fit purely into any of Vidal's taxonomies. This author assembles documentaries into four groups based on their editing techniques: hyper-editing¹ (widely used in music videos, whose editing causes a large amount of information to be concentrated in time and space); the pictorial documentary (a conventional approach to audio-visual content and language codes); the collage (which is based on combining fragments of recordings, photographs and archival footage), and the animated documentary (Vidal, 2011). Digitalisation has not only increased the production and dissemination of short films; it has also boosted the use of collage and animation since it facilitates both the assembling of footage from different sources and the production of graphic materials (Burgos Risco & Mayor Iborra, 2012). In line with the rise of digital technologies, FA's documentaries often mix the two last types of techniques –that is, collage and animation— without fitting neatly in one.

FA is not unique in mixing collage and animation. From the fields of cinema and TV series, both *Camp 14: Total Control Zone* (Wiese, 2012) –which tells about re-education camps in North Korea— and recently *El caso Alcàsser* (León, 2019) –about the kidnapping, torturing and assassination of three Spanish young women in 1992— use animations to fill the gaps that collaged footage of real events (e.g. interviews, historical recordings) cannot supply. However, FA makes extensive usage of these and other digital techniques, merging shots from news media organisations, NGOs' and activists' footage, and social media platforms content with re-enactments, animation, cartography and 3D modelling. Namely, mixing recordings of events as they happened with simulations of witnesses' remembrances.

Intelligence and content in FA films are generated by a panoply of techniques, including audio analysis, data mining, shadow projection, fluid dynamics, geolocalisation, software development, pattern analysis, photogrammetry, remote sensing, direct testimonies and interviews, and open-source intelligence (OSINT). Next, some examples of the most common methods and tools in the selected videos are examined.

Image complex and synchronisation

Data-image complex (Figure 3) combines several videos and individual snapshots, sometimes hundreds of them, to compose a single augmented image that provides

¹ *Hipermontaje* in Spanish (Vidal, 2011).

Spatio-temporal context, situational information and a scene of an event from multiple perspectives (Weizman, 2016).

[Figure 3 around here]

Figure 3: Film still, *Killing in Umm al-Hiran*, Forensic Architecture, 30:05 minutes, 2019. Courtesy of Forensic Architecture.

An image complex is achieved thanks to the synchronisation of videos and static images, which are compared, combined and synchronised using the metadata of the images to understand a scene and give it richness.

These two techniques –the image complex and the synchronisation— also reinforce the credibility of the counter-narrative that emerges from the investigation; while the images may originate from different sources, sometimes even from the authorities the documentary is disproving, they must be compatible and produce a coherent account to be combined. As FA always offers an alternative account of the facts, contradicting that of the authorities, these techniques strengthen the veracity of the story and contribute to FA’s own reliability.

FA also uses image and sound synchronisation, for example, in the *Killing in Umm al-Hiran*, as shown in Figure 4.

[Figure 4 around here]

Figure 4: Film still, *Killing in Umm al-Hiran*, Forensic Architecture, 30:05 minutes, 2019. Courtesy of Forensic Architecture.

Figure 4 shows the combination of a satellite image (periphery) with a thermal image (central), which reveals a human figure firing a weapon (the more prominent blotch in the middle) against the vehicle of the Bedouin Yaqub Musa Abu al Qi’an approaching slowly from the left. The images come from a recording made with a thermal camera and provided by the Israeli police through Facebook to support the official version of events (Forensic Architecture, 2019b). Recording with thermal cameras offer images of objects and beings that emit heat, but they do not include sound. The soundtrack of this section of the documentary comes from footage recorded on the ground during the incident, which occurred at night in almost total darkness. Right after the shooting of al Qi’an’s car, it accelerates precipitously and collides with a group of Israeli soldiers, killing one of them. A series of synchronisations of sound and images allow FA to dismantle the official version that it was a deliberate terrorist attack instead of the accidental killing of an Israeli soldier caused by the shooting of a passer-by who was in the wrong place at the wrong time.

Fluid dynamics combined with other techniques

Forensic Oceanography (FO), a team within FA dedicated to studying migration in the Mediterranean, uses fluid dynamics simulations to track the movements of objects –

usually ships— in the water. Fluid dynamics can be applied to track the evolution of the particles of a cloud formed after the fall of a bomb (as in *The bombing on Rafah* of 2014), the particles of gunpowder ejected by a fired gun and the marine currents and waves (as in *The Seizure of the Iuventa*). An example of how fluid dynamics can be combined with other techniques can be seen in Figure 5.

[Figure 5 around here]

Figure 5: Film still, *The Seizure of the Iuventa*, Forensic Oceanography, 33:45 minutes, 2018. Courtesy of Forensic Oceanography and Forensic Architecture.

Figure 5 shows how a boat full of migrants rotates on itself in reference with the horizon pushed by the waves and by the inflatable boat of the Iuventa –the main rescue ship of the German humanitarian organisation Jugend Rettet—, while the crew of the rescue boat hands over life vests to the migrants. The camera, which is focused on the operation from the Iuventa, unwittingly captures the image of other vessels in the distance (whose magnified images appear projected towards the horizon).

Among other accusations, the Italian judicial power has alleged that the crew of the Iuventa towed the empty boat to return it to the human traffickers once the rescue operation was over, contributing to the illegal immigration. The Italian authorities presented a film still showing an activist inflatable boat (on the left) apparently pulling a migrant ship (on the right) from outside the Libyan territorial waters towards the coast (Jugend Rettet, 2018, p. 8). However, FO obtained the video from which the snapshot was obtained and studied the direction of the waves and wind at the time of the operation (Figure 6), concluding that the rescue boat was dragging the empty migrant ship in the opposite direction (towards the right) in the direction of the high sea (Forensic Architecture, 2018b). Also, the metadata –information about the location and time— of the video recordings from the cameras of the Iuventa crew confirm that the rescue boat was abandoning the vessel at sea (Figure 6). Usually, the crew of the Iuventa sinks the migrant boats once it has saved the migrants; however, at the time there were several groups of migrants in the neighbourhood who needed help, and the rescuers did not have time to do so, informs the narrator of this documentary.

[Figure 6 around here]

Figure 6: Film still, *The Seizure of the Iuventa*, Forensic Oceanography, 33:45 minutes, 2018. Courtesy of Forensic Oceanography and Forensic Architecture.

3D modelling, animation and sound analysis

Most FA documentaries use 3D modelling and cartography, since, as a geoactivist organisation that focuses on architectural techniques, it puts maps and charts at the centre of its analysis and communication.

An example is Figure 7, which shows the Saydnaya prison placed on a map near Damascus, based on satellite photography.

[Figure 7 around here]

Figure 6: Film still, *Torture in Saydnaya Prison*, Forensic Architecture, 27:40 minutes, 2016. Courtesy of Forensic Architecture.

No international observer has been able to visit Saydnaya, and the prisoners are kept in darkness and silence, so that the interior of the prison has been modelled for this video on the basis of the memories of the sounds referred by the survivors, interviewed by AI and FA (e.g. steps along the corridors, water dripping, slamming doors and blows to the people being tortured), refers the narrator. FA worked with filmmaker Simone Rowat to make this documentary. Rowat had to deal with distortions in the remembrances of the survivors, as when one of the witnesses remembered having glimpsed a circular corridor from the corner of his eye while being tortured, something that the filmmaker knew was impossible from satellite photographs showing the shape of the prison (Corkery, 2018). However, the documentary shows a model of the unviable circular corridor, which is also a valuable material for the documentary.

Sometimes 3D modelling is combined with images of real events taken from footage obtained by the witnesses; the modelled sections fill information gaps in these recordings, as seen in Figure 8.

[Figure 8 around here]

Figure 8: Film still, *The Bombing of Rafah*, Forensic Architecture, 4:30 minutes, 2015. Courtesy of Forensic Architecture.

Figure 8 combines the snapshot of a video published by a journalistic organisation showing the moment in which bombs are falling with other images and a 3D model of the city. The fact that these images are not sequential (i.e. the real images following by the city model or vice versa), but that both techniques are combined in a single image shows a high degree of hybridisation. FA uses this method frequently.

When there are gaps in real footage, FA resorts in its documentaries to schematised animations with a degree of movement. One example is *Torture and Detention in Burundi* (Figure 9), which employs human figures to show how three prisoners (in red) are tormented in an episode of the torture house in Burundi. Several witnesses in the documentary confirm that these prisoners had their heads cut off, which would explain the blood trail gushing from the house.

[Figure 9 around here]

Figure 9: Film still, *Torture and Detention in Burundi*, Forensic Architecture, 22:59 minutes, 2018. Courtesy of Forensic Architecture.

FA's documentaries offer a high level of technical sophistication too; if anything, their imperfection comes from prioritising clarity to the detriment of beauty. Nevertheless, aesthetics are not neglected here; on the contrary, FA's films display stylistic coherence

in the form of a new ‘research aesthetic’ (Forensic Architecture, 2019a). Of the six ‘universal signatures’ in aesthetics established by Denis Dutton –expertise, style, criticism, imitation, particular focus and non-utilitarian pleasure (Dutton, Gaut, & McIver Lopes, 2001)—, FA’s research aesthetic exhibits five; that is, paraphrasing Dutton, virtuosity and technical artistic skill; a recognisable, unique style that combines technological adroitness and human stories; criticism and interpretation, when it produces alternative versions of events; imitation that stimulates experiences of the world in the viewers; and particular focus setting stories aside from ordinary life and using a dramatic focus of experience to instigate action. One example is, again, *The Left-to-die Boat*. In this film, the display of technology to track the ship (e.g. satellite data visualisations and cartography), the prominence of the map showing the Mediterranean sea instead of the typical human faces in human rights documentaries, the meta-narrative exposing the contradictions of the official account, the multi-layered story and the references to the gruelling experiences of the migrants confer a unique style to this documentary.

Based on the functions these techniques perform about activism, a classification is offered next, followed by a breakdown of the functions that they perform and the outcomes they can generate (Table 2).

Classification based on the techniques

Forensic architecture’s techniques accomplish several functions, both within the narration and outside it. This section examines them looking, first, at the method and data source, and second, at each technique’s function for the investigation of the events, the communication of the findings and the reception. Table 2 in the next section proposes four types of results obtained through the use of these strategies.

[Table 2 around here]

Table 2: FA’s techniques and their function. Elaborated by the author.

The data-image complex and synchronisation employed in *The Bombing of Rafah* and *Killing in Umm al-Hiran* are the result of the analysis of data obtained from footage and images taken as the events unfolded; that is, as the city of Rafah was being bombarded and the Bedouin al Qi’an was being murdered. FA does not only turn to what victims say they remember, but they also rely on what witnesses *recorded as events developed* in real-time. These recordings are then verified and synchronised, so they knit a tapestry that offers a landscape view of the investigated incidents. The data here serve two purposes: they are used to verify each other, and their combination and synchronization is employed then to communicate the story in a useful manner, since, as Kennedy and Hill point out, visual representations of data can convey complex facts and patterns quickly and effectively (Kennedy & Hill, 2017).

There is a third intended function, which is to generate counter-narratives in defiance of what the authorities say. FA exposes how the facts could be reconstructed based on real

facts and robust research methods, as opposed to what the authorities have offered. Data activism often generates unconventional stories to communicate directly to their audiences and authorities (Gutierrez 2018a). This procedure is a constant in all FA videos, both those studied in this article and in the more than forty that this organisation has produced since 2010. The counter-stories in these documentaries systematically dismantle the official narratives. Eyal Weizman, the director of FA, explains it like this:

Open verification has less access to the privilege of institutionalised truth practices, whose claims are often backed only by the authority of their respectable façades which can hide the hard and messy work of case construction (Weizman, 2019).

The soundness of the evidence put forward in these two videos reinforces too both the credibility of the story and FA's authority. In *Killing in Umm al-Hiran*, FA demolishes the official version that it was a terrorist attack and, days later, the result of the autopsy of the dead Bedouin confirms the FA account and the government is forced to go back on its version of the events (Ben Zikri, 2017). Three years after the bombing of Rafah, though, the investigation of the events was closed by Israel's military prosecution (Harel, 2018).

The fluid dynamics and other techniques employed in the Forensic Oceanography's two documentaries –*The Left-to-die Boat* and *The Seizure of the Iuventa*— help to confirm the information gathered via direct recordings of the events by both migrants and rescuers. In the first case, not one passing vessel bothered to assist the dying migrants; in the second, there was no contact or connivance between the rescuers and the traffickers. These techniques also serve to communicate the findings of the investigation: the current and wind patterns show the deadly course of the drifting left-to-die boat in the first case; in the second, the pattern analysis demonstrates that the rescuers were removing the migrant ship out of the scene, not towards the Libyan coast.

In contrast, the 3D modelling and the animations can help to reconstruct what witnesses say they remember. In *Torture and Detention in Burundi* and *Torture in Saydnaya Prison*, these re-enactments fill the gaps that direct footage cannot provide. No independent observer has ever been able to visit either the torture house in Bujumbura or the Saydnaya prison.

The same can be said about the sound analysis in *Torture in Saydnaya Prison*, based on the survivors' remembrances. An interesting point here is that FA never tries to be realistic in its recreations; instead, the intention is that these images are accurate. For example, FA does not use reconstructions in real scenarios with actors and actresses, so frequent in US true crime documentaries. FA prefers to use schematic and clear animations, as in Figure 9. The effect that this has is to clearly distinguish between the actual images obtained while the events occur without the mediation of the investigation against those that are the product of the inquiry and generated later. These recreations help FA communicate the findings of the investigation and create counter-narratives.

[Figure 10 around here]

Figure 10: Combination of recordings and recreation, and its functions. Elaborated by the author.

From the point of view of the method and the data source, two approaches emerge the employment of data from direct filming (i.e. recording) and the recreation of an event from the memories and testimonies of the survivors (i.e. recreation). From the point of view of the function, these methods serve different purposes. Direct recording tends to reinforce FA's credibility and supports their verification methods, while the recreation of events tends to have the role of filling gaps in the narrative. Both of them contribute to communicating the investigation and evidence and to the generation of counter-narratives. Although these techniques are not always applied together in all the documentaries, Figure 10 summarises their combination and effects.

Conclusions and discussion

How does Forensic Architecture and Forensic Oceanography hybridise? The hybridisation exhibited by FA and FO in nonfiction audio-visual narratives is increasingly forcing the frontiers of activism and documentaries. This hybridisation makes it challenging to catalogue FA. In line with what Treré says about digital activism, Forensic Architecture and Forensic Oceanography are situated on a hybrid terrain at the intersection between social movements, journalism and documentary, mixing not only their tools and methods but also those of other disciplines and practices in search of truths and impact. Likewise, the methodology itself becomes the protagonist of FA's narratives, since it is the basis of its capacity to generate alternative versions of events versus conventional ones or to practice a form of counter-forensics. The efforts of the Syrian, Israeli, Russian, Burundian and Italian governments and authorities involved in the cases explored by FA to impress a unique, immovable version of the facts are antagonised and challenged by the complex, sometimes cluttered, versions offered by FA. Against hegemonic, black-and-white official discourses, FA documentaries offer a multi- landscape of events, backed by facts, maps and data, which is alternative, robust and persuasive.

What are the outcomes of this hybridisation? In short, the proposals of FA go beyond borders and hybridise in a space, that of the documentary, journalism and activism, in which alternative approaches are produced, imitated and abandoned constantly (Nichols 2001: 21). Namely, technology is allowing a hybridisation in campaigns for human rights that is broadening the horizons of the documentary, journalism and activism. The result of this hybridisation –mixing recordings and recreation— serves to communicate findings effectively and to generate counter-narratives that have reception effects beyond the story, enhancing the capacity for disruption and impact offered by activism.

Declaration of interest: None

Permissions: The author has permission from Forensic Architecture and Forensic Oceanography to use the illustrations included in this article.

References

Archer, D. (2017). About. Retrieved 7 December 2017, from Archcomix website:

<http://www.archcomix.com/about/>

Ben Zikri, A. (2017). Israeli Public Security Minister Backtracks on Whether Cop's

Killing by Bedouin Was Terror. *Haaretz*. Retrieved from

<https://www.haaretz.com/israel-news/.premium-gilad-erdan-backtracks-on-whether-cop-s-killing-was-terror-1.5440064>

Bort Gual, I. (2010). Hibridación ficción-documental en las series de televisión dramáticas norteamericanas contemporáneas: a propósito de Friday Night Lights. *Asociación Cinefórum L'Atalante*, 9, 11–16.

Burgos Risco, A., & Mayor Iborra, J. (2012). Procesos de hibridación en el cine documental. *DEFORMA Cultura Online*, 1–13.

Burke, J., Borger, J., & Lewis, P. G. (2014). Israel bombards Rafah after soldier disappears amid Gaza ceasefire collapse. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/aug/01/israel-bombards-rafah-soldier-disappears-gaza-ceasefire-collapse>

Corkery, C. (2018). Turner Nominees Forensic Architecture build case for human rights. *Arts & Culture*. Retrieved from <https://www.thenational.ae/arts-culture/turner-nominees-forensic-architecture-build-case-for-human-rights-1.773543>

Dutton, D., Gaut, B., & McIver Lopes, D. (2001). Aesthetic Universals. In *The Routledge Companion to Aesthetics*. London, New York: Routledge Studies In Radical History And Politics.

- Forensic Architecture. (2018a). Project. Retrieved from <http://www.forensic-architecture.org/project/>
- Forensic Architecture. (2018b). The Seizure of The Iuventa.
- Forensic Architecture. (2019a). About. Retrieved from <https://forensic-architecture.org/about/agency>
- Forensic Architecture. (2019b). Killing in Umm al-Hiran. Retrieved from <https://forensic-architecture.org/investigation/killing-in-umm-al-hiran>
- Garcia Giribet, A. (2019). Discovering human rights through documentaries. Retrieved from Amnesty International website: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/education/2019/04/hong-kong-documentary-film-festival/>
- Garcia Rey, M., & Garrido, H. (2016, July). Datos sepultados bajo la ceniza (Metodologia). Retrieved 7 December 2016, from Civio - España en llamas website: <http://espanaenllamas.es/datos-sepultados-bajo-la-ceniza-metodologia/>
- Gutierrez, M. (2018). Maputopias: Cartographies of knowledge, communication and action in the big data society – The cases of Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia. *GeoJournal*, 84(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-018-9853-8>
- . (2020). Data activism seen from a cinematographic perspective: The hybridisations of Forensic Architecture. *Studies in Documentary Film*.
- Harel, A. (2018). IDF Closes Probe Into 2014 Gaza War’s Deadly ‘Black Friday’. *Haaretz*. Retrieved from <https://www.haaretz.com/israel-news/.premium-idf-closes-probe-into-2014-gaza-war-s-deadly-black-friday-1.6384662>
- Izod, J., Kilborn, R., & Hibberd, M. (Eds.). (2000). *From Grierson to the Docu-Soap: Breaking the Boundaries*. Luton, UK: University of Luton.

- Jugend Rettet. (2018). *Iuventa - Press Kit*. Retrieved from https://jugendrettet.org/f/files/Press%20Kit_long_EN.pdf
- Kennedy, H., & Hill, R. L. (2017). The Feeling of Numbers: Emotions in Everyday Engagements with Data and Their Visualisation. *Sociology*, 52(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038516674675>
- Kurban, C., Peña-Lopez, I., & Haberer, M. (2016). What is technopolitics? A conceptual scheme for understanding politics in the digital age. *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Internet, Law & Politics. Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Barcelona, 7-8 July, 2016*, 499–519. Retrieved from http://ictlogy.net/presentations/20160707_can_kurban_ismael_pena-lopez_maria_haberer_-_what_is_technopolitics_conceptual_scheme.pdf
- León, E. (2019). *El caso Alcàsser*.
- Lünenborg, M. (2002). *Journalism as Popular Culture Docu-Soap: A new Genre crossing the Border of Fact and Fiction*. 20. Retrieved from http://www.portalcomunicacion.com/bcn2002/n_eng/programme/prog_ind/papers/1/pdf/1006_lunen.pdf
- McNair, B. (2009). Journalism in the 21st century — evolution, not extinction. *Journalism*, 10(3).
- Nichols, B. (2001). *Introduction to Documentary*. Bloomington, US: Indiana University Press.
- PBS. (2002). Lance Loud. Retrieved from <https://www.pbs.org/lanceloud/american/>
- Sacristán, A. (2017). Realidad Virtual y Empatía Aumentada en ArtFutura 2017. *Retina*. Retrieved from https://retina.elpais.com/retina/2017/11/30/tendencias/1512025938_360911.html

- Trere, E. (2019). *Hybrid Media Activism: Ecologies, Imaginaries, Algorithms*.
Abingdon, UK: Routledge Studies In Radical History And Politics.
- Vidal, A. (2011). Nuevas tendencias formales del cine documental en el siglo XXI. *El Ojo Que Piensa. Revista de Cine Iberoamericano*, 4. Retrieved from
<http://www.elojoquepiensa.cucsh.udg.mx/index.php/elojoquepiensa/article/view/65>
- Weizman, E. (2016). Before and After Images: Eyal Weizman's The Image Complex.
Retrieved from The Photographers' Gallery Blog website:
<https://thesandpitdotorg1.wordpress.com/2016/05/22/the-image-complex/>
- Weizman, E. (2017). *Forensic Architecture: Violence at The Threshold Of Detectability*. Retrieved from
[https://calamitousannunciation.memoryoftheworld.org/Eyal%20Weizman/Forensic%20Architecture_%20Violence%20at%20\(10719\)/Forensic%20Architecture_%20Violence%20-%20Eyal%20Weizman.pdf](https://calamitousannunciation.memoryoftheworld.org/Eyal%20Weizman/Forensic%20Architecture_%20Violence%20at%20(10719)/Forensic%20Architecture_%20Violence%20-%20Eyal%20Weizman.pdf)
- Weizman, E. (2019). Open Verification. Retrieved from e-Flux Architecture website:
<https://www.e-flux.com/architecture/becoming-digital/248062/open-verification/>
- Wiese, M. (2012). *Camp 14: Total Control Zone*.
- Winston, B. (1995). *Claiming the Real: The Documentary Film Revisited*. London:
Bloomsbury Academic.
- Zimmermann, P. R. (2019). *Documentary Across Platforms: Reverse Engineering Media, Place, and Politics*. Bloomington, US: Indiana University Press.